

WAYS TO DEVELOP "GOODS-MARKET" MARKETING STRATEGIES IN FREE ECONOMIC ZONES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of developing marketing strategies in free economic zones, including the procedure for applying "good-market" strategies. Relevant proposals for the development of "goods-market" strategies in free economic zones have been developed.*

Keywords: *free economic zone, marketing strategies, "product-market" strategies, market penetration strategy, market development strategy, product development strategy, diversification strategy.*

Introduction

The beginning of the 21st century is characterized by the widespread use of such forms of international cooperation as free economic zones (hereinafter referred to as FEZs). In the context of globalization and increased economic competition between large companies, the establishment of free economic zones allows to increase the competitiveness of the national economy by using modern innovative technologies for the production and distribution of goods and services that are in high demand in the domestic and international markets.

In order to attract foreign and domestic investments in the establishment of high-tech modern productions for the deep processing of mineral raw materials and agricultural resources, which ensure the production of high-added-value competitive, quality products that are popular in foreign markets in our country. A new system of managing free economic zones and small industrial zones has been introduced in order to create a very favorable business environment, as well as comprehensive and effective use of the production and resource potential of the regions of the republic, on the basis of this, to organize new jobs and increase the income of the population, and to increase the export of local products. In particular, free economic zones have been established in our country and new ones are being established.

The use of international marketing strategies in the diversification of the production activities of the free economic zones operating in our country and the development of export activities is one of the urgent issues. Because in the countries that are leaders in free economic zones in the world, ensuring the activity of the network in the global value chain, effectively organizing international market research, developing marketing strategies for free economic zones, establishing an electronic trade system at the international level, improving the scientific and methodological foundations of increasing the reputation of national brands in the world are important directions today.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Many foreign and local economists have conducted studies on the issues of establishing free economic zones, their role and importance in the economy, and their development. In this regard, one of the foreign scientists, R. J. McCalla, states that the organization of free economic zones is a separate territory of a country in terms of the provision of logistics services and geographical location [7]. Another foreign specialist, M. Guangwen, researched the organization

of free economic zones, requirements for it, the theory and practice of economic activity in free economic zones [11]. The role of free economic zones in the national economy of the country, the organizational and economic mechanisms of free economic zones were studied in the scientific works of Ya.S. Druzik [12]. The activity of free economic zones in the international economy, the role of free economic zones in the world economy is reflected in the scientific works of N.V. Chernenko [21].

From the middle of the 20th century, the issues of organizing the activity of FEZs, increasing investment attractiveness, developing foreign trade, increasing the export potential of FEZs, which have become the main points of the economy, have been studied by foreign and local experts. Among the studies, T. Farole and F. Dobrogonov emphasized the practical aspect of these regions and said, "These structures create an opportunity for developing countries to capture additional consumer markets and increase the export potential of the countries. At the same time, he claims that these economic structures serve as a means of strengthening the processes of regional economic integration [5].

There are also studies on the geographical location of the FEZ, including regions to establish the FEZ. According to V.G.Ignatov, V.I.Butov, FEZs are limited territories, consisting of seaports and air borders. They create a favorable business environment for national and foreign businessmen in foreign trade, general economic and other areas [13].

Russian economist V. D. Adrianov has stated: "Free economic zones is a part of the national territory and creates wide opportunities for finding solutions to economic problems" [3].

Also, one of the synonymous concepts of these regions in world practice, special economic zones (SEZs), is defined by R.I. Zimenkov as follows: SEZ is a part of the national economic space. There is a special preferential economic regime for national and foreign entrepreneurs. Their task is manifested in solving socio-economic, scientific and technical problems [6].

I.R. Tazutdinov, who continued this direction, stated "FEZ is a separate part of the state, in its territory there is an institutional infrastructure, and in its territory there will be a special legal and administrative regime regulating economic relations with the outside world. " [20]. Some researchers, taking into account modern integration processes, do not give a separate definition to FEZs. In particular, we see it in the research works of V.I. Baronov and G.M. Kostyunina. In their works, the legal status of FEZs in the specific region or country where FEZs are located, and their economic situation are analyzed [9].

Advanced economists of our country approach differently, paying more attention to the preferential procedure and administrative management in FEZs. Therefore, according to the opinion of A.V. Vakhabov, Sh.Kh. Khajibakiyev, N.G. Muminov, Free Economic Zones are such geographical areas in which a preferential tax payment procedure is introduced compared to the procedure of economic activity adopted in the country. In other words, state intervention in economic processes will be reduced in this region, and it will be a part of the national economic space, and a system of certain privileges will be introduced, which are not used in other regions of the country [10].

If we look at the results of the research carried out in our country in recent years, we can see that special attention is paid to the features of FEZs that help to eliminate economic and social problems and the liberalization of the country's economic system. In particular, Sh.I. Mustafaqulov said that the free economic zone is also the image of the country. Free economic

zones serve to liberalize a country, even if they function poorly. A free economic zone is a social project in any country, in any part of it. The creation of the region not only brings additional income for the region, but also provides useful returns for the whole country in various forms [14].

Also, in A.A. Ostonakulov's opinion, the free economic zone is a territory established for use as a territorial method of economic diversification and introduction of modern technologies into the economic structure [8].

S.S. Bozarov stated that "Free economic zone is a regime that is established in an economically and geographically favorable region of the country, develops the country's economy in a comprehensive way and ensures its integration into the world economy, and includes a set of special privileges; is a specially designated area where various legal relations complicated by the foreign element are carried out" [4].

Also, we have local specialists who are conducting scientific work related to marketing issues in the free economic zones, in particular, the issues of developing marketing strategies. For example, D.H. Kholmamatov, M.Sh. Mukhiddinov carried out scientific work on the development of international marketing strategies to increase the export potential of free economic zones [15], the use of SWOT analysis in studying the activities of free economic zones [16]. Wholesale trade, marketing and logistics issues are also paid attention to a certain extent in managing the flow of goods in free economic zones [17,18]. The export geography of FEZ operating in our country, including Jizzakh FEZ, was analyzed [19].

However, the development of marketing strategies for the comprehensive development of free economic zones has not been sufficiently studied.

Analysis and results

The analysis of the world experience of the activity of special economic zones shows that their organization and development are mainly aimed at solving priority production and investment tasks, as well as at the implementation of strategic programs and projects. FEZs are usually established in regions rich in local raw materials for transport and production and with developed social infrastructure. However, the lack of development of a constructive marketing strategy for the established SEZ significantly slows down the development of FEZs.

Our research shows that ensuring the competitiveness of FEZs can be implemented only on the basis of a scientifically based marketing strategy for the development of the territory as a complex socio-economic system. At the same time, in general, the SEZ strategy can be sufficient when using a promising marketing direction - territorial marketing or regional marketing, which ensures the increase of the competitiveness of the region. The strategies of individual enterprises of SEZ residents should be developed based on the principles of marketing management, but taking into account the specific characteristics of the SEZ.

The development of marketing strategies in free economic zones is based on the following approaches:

- market segmentation;
- selection of target markets;
- finding ways to enter the market for companies operating in the SEZ;
- selection and application of marketing tools and methods;
- determining the time to market.

Based on market segmentation, each element of the market, different product groups, buyers with different behavior and requirements, regions and countries are determined.

To strengthen the position of free economic zones in the market, the following "good-market" strategies are also used:

1. "Old market - old product" (strategy of deep market penetration). Companies operating in free economic zones are achieving this by increasing the market share, reducing production and transaction costs, activating advertising, changing goals, and expanding the field of use of the manufactured product.

He defined 5 main conditions for the successful implementation of the strategy of deep penetration into the market.

Table 1

Conditions for effective use of the strategy

Situations of strategy implementation	Content
Situation 1	In the situation where the existing products in the free economic zone have not reached the level of market coverage, the source of growth is distribution and coverage of the target audience.
Situation 2	It is possible to increase the share of existing consumers in the free economic zone.
Situation 3	Due to the competitiveness of the products of the free economic zone, it is possible to obtain market share from other sources.
Situation 4	The existing economic scale of the free economic zone
Situation 5	The free economic zone has a high level of investment

2. "New market - old product" (market expansion strategy). The strategy envisages the activation of business activities at the expense of capturing new markets. In addition to new geographic markets, new market segments are constantly sought, that is, expansion and deepening of groups of consumers of these goods.

For the realization of this strategy, he distinguishes the following situations:

Table 2

Conditions for effective use of the strategy

Situations of strategy implementation	Content
Situation 1	Firms operating in free economic zones are able to enter new markets through successful experience in existing activities: when the free economic zone has unique products, unique technology, unique construction and business management, and others.
Situation 2	New markets are not saturated, barriers to market entry are low, and there is unsatisfied demand in the field in which the enterprise has been successful in the new market.
Situation 3	New markets have high growth rates.
Situation 4	The company has additional capital to develop and strengthen the free economic zone in new markets.

3. "Old market - new product" (strategy of new product production) - developing, mastering, expanding the assortment of new goods for this market, modifying goods and introducing new goods to the market, reducing the price, introducing better quality goods, selling at the same price, providing an additional guarantee to the buyer, providing consumer credit, providing additional free services and other methods of sales promotion, using direct and hidden

forms of competition.

The strategy of product development is to expand the innovation related to the current product as a result of deepening the current assortment as much as possible. If the new product can completely replace the existing product, ensure sales growth and profitability, then the profitability of the production of the new product will be high.

Table 3

Conditions for effective use of the strategy

Situations of strategy implementation	Content
Situation 1	Success in the free economic zone industry depends on innovation and continuous delivery of new products.
Situation 2	If the existing product in the free economic zone is at the maturity stage of its life cycle.
Situation 3	In the strong competition of competitors in the free economic zone
Situation 4	If a free economic zone starts a new type of activity related to a new product.

4. "New product - new market" (diversification strategy). It is the most common marketing strategy, involving the management and employees of the free economic zone and the introduction of large amounts of funds. Searching for new markets in new regions with demand for new goods, their types and models, new product range, as well as new segments in the old market where demand for new goods has arisen.

Such a strategy is implemented by firms rich in production resources, which are sufficient to produce a new product and sell it in a market not occupied by competing free economic zones. If the free economic zone intends to gain leadership in one segment of the international market, such a strategy is called single-segment concentration. If the free economic zone wants to achieve success in several segments of the international market, such a strategy is called multi-segment concentration.

Summary

Based on the results of our research, the following main conclusions were reached:

1. Marketing strategies are the use of opportunities and resources of free economic zones in the most optimal way based on the international market situation. Based on the goals of the free economic zones, marketing strategies are the fulfillment of the tasks set by the manufacturing enterprises for the individual international market and for each product. Marketing strategies are formed in order to implement production and commercial activities in full accordance with the market situation and the company's capabilities.

2. Most free economic zone strategies include growth goals: increase in sales volume, market share, revenue or size of the free economic zone. Growth is a factor that affects the activity of the free economic zone, stimulates the initiative and increases the motivation of the team and management of the free economic zone.

Growth objectives are expressed at three different levels:

- growth compared to the main market; we call it intensive growth;
- growth in relation to the production chain, "forward" or "backward" integration in relation to the main activity, this is integrative growth.

□ growth based on opportunities outside the usual area of activity: growth through diversification.

3. "Product - market" strategy is aimed at the entry of the free economic zone into new markets and the assimilation of new products. This strategy is formed depending on the opportunities of the free economic zone, products, markets, competitive situation, consumers and direction of activity. Basically, the free economic zone develops international marketing strategies for its resources and developing industries.

This strategy envisages the development of a strategy depending on the market and product renewal. The starting point is the difference between the real and planned development of the free economic zone. This means that the goal of a free economic zone cannot be achieved using the previous strategy. A goal is necessary, or it needs to be corrected, or a new strategic path must be sought.

4. Expansion of the product production portfolio of the free economic zone within the framework of the "Product-market" strategy, in particular, the production of new industrial products.

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